

Factors Associated with Musculoskeletal Disorders in Strawberry Farmers in Bedugul Agrotourism Area

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Abstract

Musculoskeletal disorders often occur in workers. One worker in the world dies every 15 seconds due to unintentional work accidents and 2 million cases of Occupational Diseases every year. Occupational health problems in Indonesia show that around 40.5% of work-related illnesses are related to musculoskeletal disorders. Musculoskeletal disorders are influenced by work posture, workload, length of service, age and BMI. The aim of this research is to find out factors related to musculoskeletal disorders in strawberry farmers in the Bedugul agrotourism area, Bali. The method used in this research is cross sectional with non-parametric statistical tests, namely bivariate chi square analysis. The research sample was all participants from the strawberry farming group in the Bedugul agrotourism area, Bali, totaling 115 farmers. The research instrument is the Nordic Body Map questionnaire which has been validated and internationally standardized by the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) Japan as a tool for measuring musculoskeletal disorders, the RULA method as a tool for measuring work posture, an oximeter as a tool for measuring pulse rate during work, digital scales and stadiometers as tools for measuring BMI. The research data were analyzed using non-parametric chi square statistics at an α value of 5%. The conclusion from the research results is that there is a significant relationship between work posture and workload on musculoskeletal disorders, there is a relationship between working years on musculoskeletal disorders and there is no relationship between age and BMI on musculoskeletal disorders.

Introduction

World Health Organization (WHO) data in 2021 reported that as many as 1.71 billion people worldwide experience musculoskeletal disorders [1]. Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are disorders or damage to joints, ligaments, muscles and other skeletal systems due to unnatural or awkward body positions, especially if done for a long and repeated duration [27] that causes decreased function, soreness or muscle pain [2].

Musculoskeletal disorders occur a lot in workers. One worker in the world dies every 15 seconds due to accidental work accidents and Occupational Diseases as many as 2 million cases every year. Occupational health problems in Indonesia show that around 40.5% of occupational diseases are related to musculoskeletal disorders [3]. Based on research conducted on 9,482 workers in 12 regencies/cities in Indonesia, disorders experienced by workers are generally in the form of

musculoskeletal diseases (16%), cardiovascular (8%), nervous disorders (5%), respiratory disorders (3%), and ENT disorders (1.5%) [4,28]. These data indicate that musculoskeletal disorders occur quite high in workers. According to data from the Central Statistics Agency of Indonesia, the most jobs in Indonesia are farmers with a total of 29.96% of 135.61 million people [5].

Farmers are one type of work that has a high risk in terms of the type of activity and work environment. Farmer work has the highest prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders of other workers, reaching 9.86% of 9.1 million workers [6]. Activities carried out by farmers include preparing earthen beds as planting media, covering beds with mulch plastic, perforating mulch plastic, planting, lifting and storing crops [29]. This activity is usually done with poor and high-risk work posture, such as sitting squatting, bending, raising hands, raising the head and others that include unnatural or awkward postures at work (awkward

More Information

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posture). This is usually done repeatedly over a long period of time for years [7,29]. One of the most famous agricultural areas in Indonesia is Bedugul which has several tourist attractions such as lakes, botanical gardens and agricultural tourism (agrotourism) where 80% of Bedugul residents work as strawberry farmers [8,29]. Most of these farmers grow crops on horticultural crops (garden plants cultivated from vegetable, fruit, to flower crops). One of the famous horticultural plant products in the Bedugul agrotourism area is strawberries which have been developed since 1986. According to research conducted by Yusuf [9] it was found that the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders in farmers in Bedugul reached 96% of the total farmers, while the most complaints were pain in the arms, legs and waist [29]. The work of strawberry farmers in the Bedugul agrotourism area has factors that increase the risk of musculoskeletal disorders such as internal factors (age, sex and body mass index, smoking and exercise habits) and external factors (work posture, workload, working period and environment) [10]. According to Castrillo et al. [11] occupational or occupational factors such as work posture, workload and working period are the main causes of musculoskeletal disorders. Age and body mass index are categorized as secondary causes of musculoskeletal disorders.

Based on external factors that trigger the risk of musculoskeletal disorders owned by storberry farmers in the Bedugul agrotourism area such as work posture, workload and working period. That poor work posture such as bending, squatting, raising hands, looking up, and so on for a long time causes continuous contractions in the muscles [4], exacerbated by excessive workload, making the pressure on the body's muscles also excessive with a long working period or more than 5 years, causing pressure to accumulate on the body. This condition can trigger an increase in the risk of musculoskeletal disorders in strawberry farmers [2]. Internal factors in strawberry growers such as age and BMI affect physiologically musculoskeletal disorders. As a person gets older, especially at the age of more than 35 years, there will be a decrease in muscle endurance and abnormalities in the intervertebral discs that trigger musculoskeletal disorders [4], especially in strawberry farmers with old age. BMI is not ideal or being overweight will make the lower back muscles contract to support weight and cause pressure on the spinal nerve pads which can increase the risk of musculoskeletal disorders, so abnormal BMI in strawberry farmers will trigger worsening of musculoskeletal disorders in strawberry farmers [12].

Image caption:

- = Researched
- = Not researched
- = Connected

Figure 1: Relationship Between Research Variable

Therefore, it is considered necessary to propose research related to factors related to musculoskeletal disorders in strawberry farmers in the Bedugul agrotourism area. The novelty of this study from other studies that have been conducted previously is specifically examining musculoskeletal disorders that occur in strawberry farmers in the agrotourism area, Bedugul as a population group that is vulnerable to musculoskeletal disorders. Although previous studies have investigated this issue in the general population or other farmers, it will specifically analyze factors relevant to strawberry growers' employment such as, poor work posture, overworkload, length of service, age linkage and BMI in strawberry growers. This makes researchers interested in taking research that discusses factors related to musculoskeletal disorders in strawberry petnai in the Bedugul agrotourism area.

Materials and Methods

This study used a quantitative research design with a type of observational analytical research using a cross-sectional research design approach. The research subjects used were all strawberry farmers in the agrotourism area of Bedugul, Bali. The sampling

technique is in the form of total sampling, with a total of 115 respondents. This research was conducted in November 2023 located in the Bedugul agrotourism area, Candi Kuning II Village, Baturiti District, Tabanan Regency. The relationship between the research variables is described as follows (Figure 1).

The research instruments used are NBM questionnaires that have been validated and international standardized by the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) Japan as a measuring instrument for musculoskeletal disorders, the Rapid Upper Limb Assesment (RULA) method as a measuring instrument for work posture [13], oxymeters as work bean measuring instruments based on the average pulse rate during work [9], and digital scales and stadiometers as BMI measuring instruments [14]. The research data obtained were analyzed using non-parametric statistics, namely bivariate chi square analysis, at a level of significance of 95% or a α value of 5%.

Results and Discussion

Results of Bivariate Analysis of Work Postures on Musculoskeletal Disorders as follow.

Table 1: Results of Bivariate Analysis of Work Postures on Musculoskeletal Disorders

Work Posture	Musculoskeletal disorder				Total		95% CI		PR	P-value
	No pain		Pain		N	%	Lower	Upper		
	n	%	n	%						
Non-risk posture	13	11,3	18	15,7	31	27	2,229	16,253	3,9	0,000
Risk posture	9	7,8	75	65,2	84	73				
Total	22	19,1	93	80,9	115	100				

Based on bivariate analysis conducted from 115 respondents, 13 respondents (11.3%) were found who did not have musculoskeletal disorders with risky work postures (11.3%), while the results of respondents who experienced musculoskeletal disorders with risky work postures were 75 respondents (65.2%). Respondents who did not have musculoskeletal disorders with risky work postures were 9 respondents (7.8%) while respondents who had musculoskeletal disorders with non risky postures were 18 respondents (15.7%). Based on the results of the chi square test, the relationship between work posture and musculoskeletal disorders obtained a significant result of 0.000 (< 0.05), meaning that Ha was accepted. These results show a significant relationship between work posture and musculoskeletal disorders in strawberry farmers. Based on the calculation of the prevalence ratio, farmers with poor work posture are 3.9 times at risk of experiencing musculoskeletal disorders. This indicates that work posture is the most dominant variable causing musculoskeletal disorders compared

to the workload variable which also has a p-value result of 0.000 but with a lower prevalence ratio. The results of this study are not in line with Tjahayuningtyas [2] who said the results of statistical test analysis obtained a value of sig = 0.864 (α = 0.05) which means that there is no relationship between work position and MSDs complaints in workers in the informal sector. Based on the value of coeff (Cramer's) = 0.029 which means that the strength of the relationship between work position and musculoskeletal complaints is low. This difference was obtained because using different work posture measurement methods, namely the OWAS method as well as different samples, namely informal workers. This result is in line with the results of Muhammad's research[15], which said there was a significant relationship between work posture and musculoskeletal disorders [30]. Supported by the results of research by Imens et al. [16] which also said therewas a relationship between work posture against musculoskeletal disorders with a p-value of <0.05 andsaid work posture was the variable that had the

greatest influence on musculoskeletal disorders. Work posture is a potential risk factor for causing musculoskeletal disorders. Poor working posture in strawberry growers can cause muscle and ligament strain, especially in the neck, shoulders, back, and hips. This is because poor work posture can cause strong muscle contractions continuously so that blood flow to

the muscles becomes not smooth and pain is felt as a symptom of musculoskeletal disorders that arise directly during or after work. Prolonged symptoms can cause worsening of musculoskeletal disorders to result in tendonitis, Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS), or Hernia Nucleus Pulposus (HNP) [4].

Table 2: Results of Bivariate Analysis of Workload Against Musculoskeletal disorders

Workload	Musculoskeletal disorder				Total		95% CI		PR	P-value
	No Pain		Pain		N	%	Lower	Upper		
	n	%	n	%						
Light to medium	16	13,9	31	27	47	40,9	1,899	14,987	3,8	0,000
Heavy to unusually heavy	6	5,2	62	53,9	68	59,1				
Total	22	19.1	93	80,9	115	100				

Based on bivariate analysis conducted from 115 respondents, 16 respondents (13.9%) did not have musculoskeletal disorders, while 62 respondents (53.9%) experienced musculoskeletal disorders with heavy to unusually heavy workloads (53.9%). Respondents who did not have musculoskeletal disorders with heavy to unusually heavy workloads were 6 respondents (5.2%) while respondents who had musculoskeletal disorders with light to moderate workloads were 31 respondents (27%).

Table 2 shows that there is a significant relationship between workload and musculoskeletal disorders with a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05) H_0 accepted. Based on the calculation of, farmers with a heavy workload of 3.8 times are at risk of experiencing musculoskeletal disorders. This result is not in line with the research of Laksono and Asyfiradayati [17] which said that based on statistical tests of the relationship between workload and musculoskeletal disorders using the spearman rank test, a p value = 0.111 (>0.05) was obtained, then H_0 was rejected so that there was no relationship between workload and musculoskeletal disorders. This difference was obtained due to differences in research samples and data analysis methods.

This research is in line with the research of Rahmania, Rovendra and Tjahayuningtyas and Aulia [2,18,19], with

the results of the analysis, obtained a value of sig = 0.000 ($\alpha = 0.05$) that there is a relationship between the workload obtained by workers and perceived musculoskeletal complaints. Based on the value of coeff (Cramer's) = 0.567 which means that there is a sufficient strength of the relationship between workload and musculoskeletal complaints which says there is a significant relationship between workload and musculoskeletal disorders in farmers [31]. Strawberry farmers are manual handling jobs in their work activities that require the use of large amounts of energy so that they often exceed the optimum muscle strength resulting in excessive muscle stretching. Muscle tension can cause disturbances in blood circulation which then causes tingling or muscle pain.

Inappropriate or excessive workload can result in physical and mental stress on workers, which can also contribute to the development of musculoskeletal disorders that can increase the risk of back injuries, lumbar injuries, epicondylitis (tennis and golf elbow syndrome), carpal tunnel syndrome, and more [20]. To compensate for the workload of farmers who are classified as heavy workloads, they must be interspersed with periodic breaks with sufficient time intervals.

Table 3: Results of Working Time Bivariate Analysis Against Musculoskeletal Disorders

Period of Service	Musculoskeletal disorder				Total		95% CI		PR	P-value
	No Pain		Pain		N	%	Lower	Upper		
	n	%	n	%						
Low risk	16	13,9	44	38,3	60	52,2	1,068	8,258	2,4	0,032
High risk	6	5,2	49	42,6	55	47,8				
Total	22	19.1	93	80,9	115	100				

Based on bivariate analysis conducted from 115 respondents, 16 respondents (13.9%) did not have musculoskeletal disorders with high-risk work periods (42.6%), while 49 respondents (42.6%) experienced

musculoskeletal disorders (42.6%). Respondents who did not have musculoskeletal disorders with a high-risk working period were 6 respondents (5.2%) while

respondents who had musculoskeletal disorders with a low-risk working period were 44 respondents (38.3%). The relationship between working period and musculoskeletal disorders based on the results of the analysis in table 4.13 with a p-value result of 0.032 (<0.05) found a relationship between the length of work and the risk of musculoskeletal disorders. Based on the calculation of the prevalence ratio of farmers who have a long working period or classified as working period with high risk, 2.4 times the risk of experiencing musculoskeletal disorders. This study is not in line with Muhammad and Febriana [10,15] who said there was no relationship between working time and musculoskeletal disorders with p-values of 0.164 and 0.448. The absence of a relationship is possible because the average worker has a working period of <5 years so

that not many workers have a working period of more than >5 years.

This study is in line with the research of Herlyani Khosama [21] who said there is a significant association or relationship between working life and musculoskeletal disorders in a person. The length of work can cause the accumulation of one's work activities carried out in a long period of time, if these activities are carried out continuously for a period of years, it can certainly cause clinical or chronic fatigue that causes disruption to the body. Working period can cause a continuous static load if workers do not pay attention to ergonomic factors, it will cause musculoskeletal disorders [22,32].

Table 4: Results of age bivariate analysis of musculoskeletal disorders

Age	Musculoskeletal disorder				Total		95% CI		PR	P-value
	No Pain		Pain		N	%	Lower	Upper		
	n	%	n	%						
Low Risk	10	8,7	36	31,3	46	40	0,517	3,368	1,2	0,561
Higg Risk	12	10,4	57	49,6	69	60				
Total	22	19,1	93	80,9	115	100				

Based on bivariate analysis conducted from 115 respondents, 10 respondents (8.7%) did not have musculoskeletal disorders with a low-risk age (8.7%), while 57 respondents (49.6%) experienced musculoskeletal disorders (49.6%). Respondents who did not have musculoskeletal disorders with a high risk age were 12 respondents (10.4%) while respondents who had musculoskeletal disorders with a low risk age were 36 respondents (31.3%).

Based on Table 4, a p-value of 0.561 (>0.05) was found to have no relationship between age and musculoskeletal disorders. Although based on the calculation of the prevalence ratio, the risk level was obtained 1.2 times the occurrence of musculoskeletal disorders in farmers classified as high-risk age or age >35, this risk level was not significant because a p-value of >0.05 was obtained. These results indicate no association between age and musculoskeletal disorders in strawberry growers. This is contrary to the results of previous research conducted by Shobur et al. and Sumigar et al. [3,6] which states that there is a significant relationship between age at risk (≥35 years) and musculoskeletal disorders, with p-value is 0.000 (p-value is 0.000 (p<0.05) and correlation (r) = 0.549 which means the strength of the correlation between age and musculoskeletal complaints is moderate and the direction of correlation in this study is positive which means the higher the age, the higher the musculoskeletal complaints. The results of this study were different because of differences in samples and how to analyze data.

However, the results of this study are in line with Krismayani & Muliawan [23] who said age and BMI did not have a meaningful relationship with musculoskeletal disorders with a p-value of 0.76 (p>0.05) it was said that there was no meaningful relationship between age and complaints of MSDs, likely due to uneven frequency distribution, where most (78.57%) respondents in Krismayani & Muliawan's study were aged ≥35. In addition, MSDs complaints are not only felt in respondents aged ≥35 years, but these complaints are also widely felt in respondents aged <35 years. This is due to unnatural or poor work posture when working both in respondents with the age of ≥35 years and the age of <35 years.

One of the triggers for musculoskeletal disorders is the formation of lactic acid in the muscles during work, this lactic acid will later be broken down by the body's metabolism at rest. Even in someone with old age, if they have a good body metabolism without any disease that can affect the body's metabolism, the breakdown of lactic acid will still occur even though it will take longer[24]. This is the reason why there is no meaningful relationship between age and musculoskeletal disorders in this study. In addition, based on observations at the time of the study that musculoskeletal disorders were not only felt in respondents aged >35 years, but these complaints were also widely felt in respondents aged ≤35 years. This is also influenced by other factors such as poor

work posture during farming both in respondents aged >35 years and aged ≤35 years.

Table 5: Results of BMI bivariate analysis of musculoskeletal disorders

BMI	Musculoskeletal disorder				Total		95% CI		PR	P-value
	No Pain		Pain		N	%	Lower	Upper		
	n	%	n	%						
≤ 22,9 (underweight-normal)	13	11,3	42	36,5	22	47,8	0,683	4,503	6,1	0,240
>22,9 (overweight-obesitas)	9	7,8	51	44,4	93	52,2				
Total	55	19,1	60	80,9	115	100				

Based on bivariate analysis conducted from 115 respondents, it was found that respondents who did not have musculoskeletal disorders with BMI ≤22.9 (underweight to normal) as many as 13 respondents (11.3%), while the results of respondents who experienced musculoskeletal disorders with BMI >22.9 (overweight and obesity) were 51 respondents (44.4%). Respondents who did not have musculoskeletal disorders with BMI >22.9 (overweight and obesity) were 9 respondents (7.8%) while respondents who had musculoskeletal disorders with BMI ≤22.9 (underweight to normal) were 42 respondents (36.5%). In the BMI variable, a p-value of 0.240 was obtained that there was no significant relationship between BMI and musculoskeletal disorders (p>0.05). Although based on the calculation of the prevalence ratio, strawberry farmers with a BMI of >22.9 (overweight and obesity) have a risk of 6.1 times experiencing musculoskeletal disorders, this level of risk is not significant because a p-value of >0.05 is obtained. This result is in line with research conducted by Krismayani & Muliawan [23], which states that there is no relationship between BMI and musculoskeletal disorders (p > 0.05) There is no relationship between BMI and MSDs complaints according to Krismayani and Muliawan due to the uneven distribution of respondents' frequency, where most respondents have BMI categorized as not risky or ≤22, 9 (normal BMI) as many as 30 people (71.43%).

Based on theory, BMI is one of the factors that can influence the occurrence of musculoskeletal disorders. The heavier a person is, the higher the risk of developing musculoskeletal disorders [25]. However, according to Septiani [24], musculoskeletal disorders in workers are also influenced by their workload, even though these workers have a normal BMI if their workload is classified as a heavy workload, the risk of developing musculoskeletal disorders remains high [24]. The same thing was also said by Ramdan & laksamono [26] disorders of the musculoskeletal system associated with BMI, influenced by the condition of the balance of the skeletal structure in receiving loads, not only body weight but also other additional loads received including workload.

So that there is no relationship between BMI and musculoskeletal disorders in this study can be said because the workload of strawberry farmers is classified as a heavy workload which can also increase the risk of musculoskeletal disorders in farmers who have normal BMI. In addition, based on observations, it was found that the frequency distribution of respondents based on BMI was uneven, where most respondents had BMI categorized as non-risky (normal BMI) as many as 83 people (72.2%), and farmers who had normal BMI also experienced many musculoskeletal disorders.

Conclusion

The results of research with the chi-square test showed a significant relationship between work posture and musculoskeletal disorders, namely strawberry farmers who had poor work posture had a 3.9 higher risk when compared to strawberry farmers who had good work posture with p-value 0.000. The results of the study with the chi-square test showed a significant relationship between workload and musculoskeletal disorders, namely strawberry farmers who had a heavy workload had a 3.8 higher risk when compared to strawberry farmers who had a light workload with a p-value of 0.000. The results of the study with the chi-square test showed a significant relationship between working period and musculoskeletal disorders, namely strawberry farmers with a working period of >5 years had a 2.4 higher risk when compared to strawberry farmers with a working period of ≤5 years with a p-value of 0.032. The results of the study with the chi-square test showed no relationship between age and musculoskeletal disorders, namely strawberry farmers aged ≤35 years also had a risk of experiencing musculoskeletal disorders with a p-value of 0.561. The results of the study with the chi-square test showed no relationship between BMI and musculoskeletal disorders, namely strawberry farmers who had a normal BMI also had a risk of experiencing musculoskeletal disorders with a p-value of 0.240.

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